

Main Theme Report

by the chair, Hubert-Jan Henket

The city is the result of intellectual development and material requirements over time, argued Jean Louis Cohen. A variation on this was given by Hilde Heynen (see page 120) of these proceedings) referring to Sibyl Moholy Nagy who wrote that the city is the result of the collective desire for that city and thus citizens should participate in the forming of their city. The Brazilian social geographer Milton Santos presented a clear underpinning for these theses talking about the South American Metropole. The city is a living organism, he said, in which the artefacts are static and human action is transient. So whatever happens the physical structure is always outdated in relation to the socio economic requirements and greed. How to get this into a workable and democratically controllable system? One thing to him was clear: large scale and total concepts will not do because money flows in any direction where profit can be made leaving behind what is not needed any longer.

Yet, Jean Louis Cohen pointed out, the contradiction between radical global plans and local discussion was the most striking peculiarity of Modern Movement Urbanism. A very striking demonstration of this argument was presented by Fernando Perez Oyarzun. He showed Le Corbusier's scheme of 1929 for a viaduct of 45 km long structure radically solving the urban traffic problem in a mountain environment as well as solving the housing shortage. How disastrous this project would have been if (only partly) realised, seen through the eyes of Cohen, Santos, or Moholy Nagy? One was reminded of the peculiar contradiction in Corbu's work between his extreme sensitivity in some projects (take for example 'The Currutchet House in la Plata Argentina) and his extreme radicalism in this case. But more importantly one wondered what influence this scheme has had on the development of the South American city. Before the arrival of Le Corbusier, South America cities had a similar scale to their European brothers. But inspired by the vastness of the South American landscape Corbu changed his concept of scale and it seems that his local disciples adopted this concept to put it into practice.

Countering a question from the audience how to approach the conservation of Modern Movement

cities like Brasilia, Cohen said 'you can't conserve a social structure'.

Later on Jadish Sagar in his beautiful presentation on Chandigahr (see page 302) of these proceedings) developed this argument further. It is unavoidable that the values of the mix with new needs and provided extremes are reconciled or at least if plurality is accepted the outcome can be influenced in a positive and constructive way.